

BLUEVISION

D1.2 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Sustainable predictive maintenance for circular material preservation and human-centric remote-operations in maritime critical infrastructures via augmented reality and digital twins
BLUEVISION

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D1.2 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN Version 1.0

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Executive summary

This document serves as the official Data Management Plan (DMP) for the BLUEVISION project. Its primary purpose is to clearly define and explain the overarching data management strategy that will be implemented throughout the project's 36-month lifecycle. This plan details the methodologies and standards that the consortium will use to collect, structure, store, and process data.

A central focus of this DMP is ensuring full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other applicable EU, international, and national data protection laws. Because BLUEVISION involves extensive engagement with end-users—such as conducting surveys, and generating advanced learner analytics via the project's digital platform—this document outlines strict confidentiality protocols to safeguard personal privacy, ensure proper informed consent, and handle primary data securely.

In strict alignment with the project's commitment to transparency and accessible education, the DMP outlines the open-access rules governing the project's results. **To ensure seamless compliance with EU open-science mandates, this plan was structured using the ARGOS data management tool.** It ensures that all non-sensitive outputs and educational materials produced by BLUEVISION are made fully available to the public under an open Creative Commons license, with hosting facilitated through EU open-access platforms such as Zenodo and OpenAIRE.

Finally, to support BLUEVISION's core objective of fostering inclusion in the maritime and deep-tech sectors, this plan establishes the guidelines and protocols for monitoring diversity and gender inclusion data throughout the project's activities.

1 Templates

1.1 Descriptions

1.1.1 WP3 Dataset

Dataset about Entrepreneurial maritime incubators, sustainable predictive maintenance Competence Framework and Occupational Profiles along with skills ecosystem platform

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

- 1.1 Brief description of the described research output
 - 1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?*

Other

- 1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?*

Digital

- 1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?*

New

- 1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?*

Observational

Learner self-declared data

- 1.1.5 What is its format?*

Text, numerical

- 1.1.6 What is its expected size?*

tbd

- 1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?*

- To keep on record

- To make informed decisions

To enable a better development of the microcredential system.

- 1.1.8 *What is its origin / provenance?*

User provided data via online questionnaires/workshops.

- 1.1.9 *To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?*

Education

Trainers

- 2 Links Between Outputs

- 2.1 Publications

- 2.1.1 *Does the described output support any scientific publication?*

No

- 2.1.2 *Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?*

No

- 2.2 Datasets

- 2.2.1 *Does the described output use or support any published dataset?*

No

- 2.3 Software

- 2.3.1 *Does the described output use or support any software?*

No

- 3 FAIR Practices
 - 3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?*
 - Data identifiers
 - Other
 - Handle
 - Personally Identifiable Information (PII)
 - Device Identifiers (such as IP address or MAC address)
 - Credentials (such as private keys or AWS secret access keys)
 - 3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?*
 - No
 - 3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible
 - 3.2.1 Repository
 - 3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?*
 - Zenodo
 - 3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?*
 - Yes
 - Follows repository standards

- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Through Zenodo Community

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Zenodo Community

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Private data will be closed.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Tbd

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

We will curate the main information of the output in the form of metadata.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

TBD

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbd

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 *How will this cost be covered?*

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 *Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output*

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP Leader

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 *What security measures are followed?*

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Other
- Physical access control

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the BLUEVISION project.

5.1.2 *What conditions do the security measures meet?*

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

- 5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the BLUEVISION project.

- 6 Ethical Aspects

- 6.1 Ethical aspects

- 6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Sensitive data will be closed due to legal reasons.

- 6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

- 6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

- 6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- National laws

Yes

- 7 Other Issues

- 7.1 Other

- 7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

1.1.2 WP6 Dataset

Dataset about monitoring and evaluation

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 *What kind of research output are you describing?*

Other

1.1.2 *Is it physical or digital?*

Digital

1.1.3 *Are you generating or re-using it?*

New

1.1.4 *What is the type of the described dataset?*

Derived or compiled

Structured QA data (self-reported) by project partners, participants and external evaluator

1.1.5 *What is its format?*

Text, Numerical

1.1.6 *What is its expected size?*

tbd

1.1.7 *Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?*

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

- To develop a product

Data will be used to improve project processes/outcomes.

- 1.1.8 *What is its origin / provenance?*

From the project partners & external evaluator

- 1.1.9 *To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?*

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy

- 2 Links Between Outputs

- 2.1 Publications

- 2.1.1 *Does the described output support any scientific publication?*

No

- 2.1.2 *Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?*

No

- 2.2 Datasets

- 2.2.1 *Does the described output use or support any published dataset?*

No

- 2.3 Software

- 2.3.1 *Does the described output use or support any software?*

No

- 3 FAIR Practices
 - 3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?*
 - Data identifiers
 - Researchers identifiers
 - Organizations identifiers
 - Projects identifiers
 - Handle
 - ORCID
 - Other
 - Cordis
 - 3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?*
 - No
 - 3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible
 - 3.2.1 Repository
 - 3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?*
 - Zenodo
 - 3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?*
 - Yes
 - 3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?*
 - Yes
 - 3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?*
 - yes

3.2.1.7 *Does the repository support versioning?*

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 *How is the dataset / output shared?*

Closed

3.2.2.3 *What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?*

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 *Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?*

No

3.2.2.8 *Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?*

No

3.2.2.9 *Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends*

Tbd

3.2.2.10 *Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for*

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 *Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?*

No

3.2.3.2 *Under which license will metadata be provided?*

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 *Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?*

No

3.2.3.4 *Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?*

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 *Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?*

No

3.3.2 *If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?*

3.3.3 *Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?*

No

3.3.4 *Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?*

No

3.3.7 *Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?*

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 *What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?*

CC0 1.0

- 3.4.2 *What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?*

Data cleaning

- 3.4.3 *Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?*

No

- 3.4.4 *Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?*

No

- 3.4.5 *Is provenance well documented?*

Yes

- 3.4.6 *What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?*

Data conform to format specification

- 4 Allocation of Resources

- 4.1 Allocation of resources

- 4.1.1 *What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?*

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

- 4.1.2 *How will this cost be covered?*

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

- 4.1.3 *Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output*

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 *Do you make use of other procedures for data management?*

No

1.1.3 WP7 Dataset

Dataset about communication and dissemination.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 *What kind of research output are you describing?*

Other

1.1.2 *Is it physical or digital?*

Digital

1.1.3 *Are you generating or re-using it?*

New

1.1.4 *What is the type of the described dataset?*

Derived or compiled

Registration lists from people participating in dissemination actions, photos, videos + aggregated dissemination metrics.

1.1.5 *What is its format?*

Text, Numerical, Images, Videos

1.1.6 *What is its expected size?*

tbd

1.1.7 *Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?*

- To obtain information

- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to engagement and impact achievement.

1.1.8 *What is its origin / provenance?*

From the participants + from social media platforms (including website).

1.1.9 *To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?*

- Researchers
- Education

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 *Does the described output support any scientific publication?*

No

2.1.2 *Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?*

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 *Does the described output use or support any published dataset?*

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 *Does the described output use or support any software?*

No

- 3 FAIR Practices
 - 3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1.1 *What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?*
 - Data identifiers
 - Researchers identifiers
 - Organizations identifiers
 - Projects identifiers
 - Handle
 - ORCID
 - Other
 - Cordis
 - 3.1.1.2 *Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?*
 - No
 - 3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible
 - 3.2.1 Repository
 - 3.2.1.1 *In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?*
 - Zenodo
 - 3.2.1.2 *Is the selected repository a trusted source?*
 - Yes
 - 3.2.1.5 *Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?*
 - Yes
 - 3.2.1.6 *Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?*
 - yes

3.2.1.7 *Does the repository support versioning?*

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 *How is the dataset / output shared?*

Closed

3.2.2.3 *What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?*

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 *Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?*

No

3.2.2.8 *Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?*

No

3.2.2.9 *Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends*

Tbd

3.2.2.10 *Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for*

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 *Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?*

No

3.2.3.2 *Under which license will metadata be provided?*

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 *Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?*

No

3.2.3.4 *Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?*

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 *Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?*

No

3.3.2 *If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?*

3.3.3 *Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?*

No

3.3.4 *Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?*

No

3.3.7 *Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?*

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 *What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?*

CC0 1.0

- 3.4.2 *What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?*

Data cleaning

- 3.4.3 *Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?*

No

- 3.4.4 *Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?*

No

- 3.4.5 *Is provenance well documented?*

Yes

- 3.4.6 *What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?*

Data conform to format specification

- 4 Allocation of Resources

- 4.1 Allocation of resources

- 4.1.1 *What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?*

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

- 4.1.2 *How will this cost be covered?*

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

- 4.1.3 *Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output*

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 *Do you make use of other procedures for data management?*

No

1.1.4 WP5 Dataset

Dataset about Piloting maritime skills ecosystems and entrepreneurial incubators

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

- 1 Summary
 - 1.1 Brief description of the described research output
 - 1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?*
Other
 - 1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?*
Digital
 - 1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?*
New
New data coming from:

Task 5.2 - Train the trainer attendance sheets (again registration list)

Task 5.3 - attendance sheet for the learners' pilot + "test how learners get familiarised with the competences from WP2 and what challenges they encounter in the work-based learning process" (I assume this will be a structured data survey).

Task 5.4 & Task 5.5 - this will be conceptual work based on industry cases, so no real data will be generated (all pilots will be done on secondary datasets - no new data).

Task 5.6 - Comparative evaluation report - comprising of pre-post training needs testing (this will generate some structured data)

Task 5.7 - Massive virtual pilots (again registration lists) + in this case user-generated data (structured quantitative evaluations of BLUEVISION products)

1.1.4 *What is the type of the described dataset?*

Derived or compiled

Task 5.2 - Train the trainer attendance sheets (again registration list)

Task 5.3 - attendance sheet for the learners' pilot + "test how learners get familiarised with the competences from WP2 and what challenges they encounter in the work-based learning process" (I assume this will be a structured data survey).

Task 5.4 & Task 5.5 - this will be conceptual work based on industry cases, so no real data will be generated (all pilots will be done on secondary datasets - no new data).

Task 5.6 - Comparative evaluation report - comprising of pre-post training needs testing (this will generate some structured data)

Task 5.7 - Massive virtual pilots (again registration lists) + in this case user-generated data (structured quantitative evaluations of BLUEVISION' products)

1.1.5 *What is its format?*

Text, Numerical, Videos, Images

1.1.6 *What is its expected size?*

tbd

1.1.7 *Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?*

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

- To develop a product

Data will be used to improve the learning content & test the project products.

- 1.1.8 *What is its origin / provenance?*

From the participants

- 1.1.9 *To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?*

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy

- 2 Links Between Outputs

- 2.1 Publications

- 2.1.1 *Does the described output support any scientific publication?*

No

- 2.1.2 *Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?*

No

- 2.2 Datasets

- 2.2.1 *Does the described output use or support any published dataset?*

No

- 2.3 Software

- 2.3.1 *Does the described output use or support any software?*

No

- 3 FAIR Practices
 - 3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?*
 - Data identifiers
 - Researchers identifiers
 - Organizations identifiers
 - Projects identifiers
 - Handle
 - ORCID
 - Other
 - Cordis
 - 3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?*
 - No
 - 3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible
 - 3.2.1 Repository
 - 3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?*
 - Zenodo
 - 3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?*
 - Yes
 - 3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?*
 - Yes
 - 3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?*
 - yes

3.2.1.7 *Does the repository support versioning?*

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 *How is the dataset / output shared?*

Closed

3.2.2.3 *What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?*

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.5 *Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?*

No

3.2.2.8 *Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?*

No

3.2.2.9 *Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends*

Tbd

3.2.2.10 *Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for*

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 *Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?*

No

3.2.3.2 *Under which license will metadata be provided?*

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 *Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?*

No

3.2.3.4 *Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?*

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 *Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?*

No

3.3.2 *If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?*

3.3.3 *Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?*

No

3.3.4 *Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?*

No

3.3.7 *Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?*

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 *What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?*

CC0 1.0

- 3.4.2 *What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?*

Data cleaning

- 3.4.3 *Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?*

No

- 3.4.4 *Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?*

No

- 3.4.5 *Is provenance well documented?*

Yes

- 3.4.6 *What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?*

Data conform to format specification

- 4 Allocation of Resources

- 4.1 Allocation of resources

- 4.1.1 *What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?*

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

- 4.1.2 *How will this cost be covered?*

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

- 4.1.3 *Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output*

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 *Do you make use of other procedures for data management?*

No

1.1.5 WP4 Dataset

Dataset about BLUEVISION digital platform

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Other

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Tracked learning experience data

1.1.5 What is its format?

- Text files
- Numerical

- Other

(i.e. time spent on learning content, performance during online evaluations, relevance of the modelled PM strategies in SCEnAT, performance during Teaching Factories, trainer observations during the workbased learning pilots, issues encountered, platform usage ability, etc)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

To enable the trainers to better help the learners shape their own learning paths and improve the training value.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

BLUEVISION platform

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Education
- Other

Trainers

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

- 3 FAIR Practices
 - 3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata
 - 3.1.1.1 *What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?*

Data identifiers

Handle

- Personally Identifiable Information (PII)
- Device Identifiers (such as IP address or MAC address)
- Credentials (such as private keys or AWS secret access keys)
- Financial information (such as credit card numbers)

- 3.1.1.2 *Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?*

No

- 3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

- 3.2.1 Repository

- 3.2.1.1 *In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?*

Will be uploaded to Zenodo

- 3.2.1.2 *Is the selected repository a trusted source?*

Yes

3.2.2 Data 3.2.2.2 *How is the dataset / output shared?*

Open

However, sensitive data will be closed due to legal reasons.

 3.2.2.9 *Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends*

Through Zenodo Community

 3.2.2.10 *Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for*

At least 2 years.

 3.2.3 Metadata 3.2.3.1 *Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?*

Yes

We will curate the main information of the output in the form of metadata.

 3.2.3.2 *Under which license will metadata be provided?*

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

 3.2.3.4 *Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?*

Yes

Metadata may be transcribed to Zenodo or other open repository.

 3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable 3.3.1 *Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?*

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

TBD

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Zenondo may be a good alternative.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

TBD

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security
- Other

TBD

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

5 Security 5.1 Data Security *5.1.1 What security measures are followed?*

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Other
- Physical access control

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the BLUEVISION project.

 6 Ethical Aspects 6.1 Ethical aspects *6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?*

yes

Sensitive data will be closed due to legal reasons.

 6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

 6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

 6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies

- Other

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 *Do you make use of other procedures for data management?*

No

1.1.6 WP2 Dataset

Dataset about micro-courses in Deep-tech driven sustainable predictive maintenance in maritime (SPMM) training related to the Europass Digital Credentials framework

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 *What kind of research output are you describing?*

Other

1.1.2 *Is it physical or digital?*

Digital

1.1.3 *Are you generating or re-using it?*

New

1.1.4 *What is the type of the described dataset?*

Derived or compiled

Registration lists from people participating in the foresight workshops & their insights / know-how related to raising skills.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Text

Numerical

Image

Video/Audio

Other

(i.e. time spent on creating content and familiarizing with tools, performance during online evaluations and workshops, adaptation and application of the design-thinking model of the TraCCE (2020) project, selective establishment of working groups, peer review results, content and learning pace adjustments for certifications, performance on VET Certification, performance on Higher Education Certification, trainer observations on train-the-trainers content, issues encountered, etc.)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

tbd

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

Data will be used to establish the learner profiles.

Data will be used to provide certified qualifications.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

From the participants

From the researchers

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Education
- Economy
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets 2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

 2.3 Software 2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

 3 FAIR Practices 3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata 3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata 3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

Handle

ORCID

Other

Cordis

 3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

 3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible 3.2.1 Repository 3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 *Is the selected repository a trusted source?*

Yes

3.2.1.5 *Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?*

Yes

3.2.1.6 *Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?*

yes

3.2.1.7 *Does the repository support versioning?*

Unknown

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 *How is the dataset / output shared?*

Closed

The dataset includes sensitive data and personal information

3.2.2.3 *What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?*

Personal data is involved.

3.2.2.8 *Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?*

No

3.2.2.9 *Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends*

Tbd

3.2.2.10 *Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for*

2 years

3.2.3 Metadata 3.2.3.1 *Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?*

Yes

We will curate the main information of the output in the form of metadata.

 3.2.3.2 *Under which license will metadata be provided?*

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

 3.2.3.3 *Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?*

Yes

 3.2.3.4 *Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?*

Yes

Metadata may be transcribed to Zenodo or other open repository.

 3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable 3.3.1 *Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?*

No

 3.3.2 *If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?* 3.3.3 *Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?*

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

TBD

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Data cleaning

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Perhaps Zenodo

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

tbc

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

WP leader

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Other

More security measures will be added.

TBD within the implementation of the BLUEVISION project.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

Personal/sensitive data

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- Other

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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